

THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS AND NEURAL NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLIGENT ENERGY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Power electronics-based power system technology, called the smart grid, is fundamental to renewable energy systems because the intermittent nature of renewable energy affects the output characteristics of generators and converters and must be compensated for by integration with energy storage.

Keywords: intelligent power system; artificial intelligence; power electronics; management methods.

Operators of conventional generation systems based on hydro and thermal plants can relatively easily determine the optimal settings for generating units to meet daily load changes. Obviously, this is not possible for electrical networks with a large share of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind farms. Therefore, large stores of energy storage devices must compensate for their volatility. Power electronics-based energy systems enable smarter energy systems, and artificial intelligence (AI) maintains high performance and reliability, high efficiency in line with emerging technologies, including water, food, bio-resources, renewable energy, waste, where smart grid systems promote ecosystems to human services through the circular economy paradigm. In the future, the evolution of the power system must take place, from unidirectional power flow, existing technologies, to the future bidirectional power supply with integrated communications and developed infrastructure. The energy system is developing due to the transfer of energy supply from large central generating stations to smaller distributed energy resources [1].

Power electronics-based energy systems enable smarter energy systems, while artificial intelligence (AI) maintains high performance and reliability, high efficiency in line with evolving technologies. Wind power production has grown exponentially over the past few years. In the United States, rated installed wind power capacity has more than doubled in the past decade. The first wind turbine for was a 50 kW turbine installed in the early 1980s. Currently, by 2020, wind turbines with a rated output of

up to 10 MW are available on the market. Moreover, turbines with a capacity of 15–20 MW are under development.

The integration and operation of multiple bi-directional power electronic systems in large networks is a complex engineering challenge. The AI-based control system is seen as a tool to help manage such complex systems to ensure optimal and safe operation, i.e. optimization of operation not only to achieve the best economic performance, but also, more difficult, to minimize the risk of cascading outages and accidents. However, implementing AI-based control to maintain system safety will require accurate power system models to test the effects of multiple accidents and predict optimal control actions such as load and line switching, transformer tap changer settings, and many other parameters. The model will also be required to train the artificial intelligence fuzzy logic system. An artificial intelligence system will also be needed to check the accuracy of system models and their changes over time due to failures, equipment aging and maintenance [2]. Power electronics enable renewable energy integration and AI-based controllers will ensure that these complex systems operate optimally, and rapid simulation with accurate models will be mandatory to implement, design and test an AI-based system.

Artificial intelligence is a broad and comprehensive field, consisting of machine learning, logic-based tools, information and rules, and probabilistic methods. Control strategies for microgrids and smart grids will enable bi-directional power flow, regulate power distribution between distributed generators, and meet power quality requirements. There are many examples of the use of artificial intelligence algorithms in forecasting tasks. For example, the dependence of renewable energy generation on weather conditions has greatly increased the need for accurate forecasting.

In Germany, the German company Schleswig-Holstein Netz AG, which operates electrical networks, uses artificial intelligence methods (a self-learning network) to determine the location of suspected faults. As initial data, information on the service life of electrical network elements and repairs carried out, as well as information on loads and weather conditions are used [3].

In the United States, unmanned aerial vehicles are used to survey the condition of high-voltage power lines and wind turbines, controlled by software with artificial intelligence algorithms to process the monitoring results. The neural network helps to better solve the problem of pattern recognition, for which, during the training process, thousands of images of damaged wind turbines are loaded into the program (including the consequences of lightning strikes, delamination, coating erosion, etc.).

There are three frameworks with some function generalization that can be used for AI-based power conversion systems: (1) function approximation or I/O mapping, (2) feedback control, and (3) system optimization. The first is to build a model using

heuristic or numerical data, the second is to compare the setpoint with an output signal that can be measured or estimated using a function that minimizes the setpoint error, and the third is to look for system parameters and conditions that will maximize or minimize this feature. Fuzzy logic and neural networks make the implementation of these three structures possible, stable and reliable in practical applications. The integration of modern power electronics, energy systems, communication, information and cyber technologies with a high level of penetration of renewable energy sources is at the forefront of the development and implementation of smart grid technology [4].

Traditional control consists of several methods for designing controllers for dynamic systems. All of them require a mathematical formulation of the controlled system and a specific approach to be used to develop feedback control. Here are some of these methods [5]:

- PID control: over 90% of controllers in use today are PID controllers (or at least some form of PID controller such as P, PI or PD controller). This approach is often considered simple, reliable and understandable;
- construction of Bode diagrams and Nyquist hodograph - root locus;
- state-space methods: feedback and observers;
- optimal control based on Pontryagin's maximum principle and Bellman's dynamic programming method;
- nonlinear methods: feedback linearization, synthesis of nonlinear control systems based on Lyapunov functions, sliding mode control;
- adaptive control: reference adaptive control, self-tuning controllers and non-linear adaptive control;
- stochastic control: minimum dispersion control, stochastic adaptive control.

Unfortunately, using some of these traditional control approaches, engineers are somewhat isolated from the control problem itself and become increasingly involved in mathematics; this usually allows unrealistic control laws to be developed.

Neural networks can be used to predict power consumption, simulate load distribution in large power systems, study non-linear functions in power electronics and power systems, evaluate poorly modeled systems, for example: the effect of temperature change on the rotor resistance of an induction motor, the non-linear response of capacitors, the simulation of losses in the core of a transformer, life expectancy of protection circuits, and many other problems in which it is usually very difficult to approximate a function using pure mathematical theory [6].

The term neuro-fuzzy systems and neuro-fuzzy methods or models refers to a combination of neural network and fuzzy systems methods, in which a fuzzy system is usually created from data using some kind of heuristic learning procedure used in neural networks. These systems are usually used for function approximation problems.

The manual design of a fuzzy system requires a structure (a set of rules), which is usually built on the basis of trial and error, and experience based on the operational knowledge of the system. ANFIS is a class of networks that are functionally equivalent to fuzzy inference systems that create a powerful intelligent system with improved design and performance characteristics [7].

Modern distribution generation facilities have widespread advanced metering infrastructure, global monitoring systems and other control systems. Huge data (Big Data) is available that can be used for model development and training in artificial intelligence applications. Deep learning methods and architectures are powerful tools for improving the accuracy of solar and wind generation forecasts based on large datasets, providing efficient solutions for soft source control, load forecasting. Smart meters provide data that reflects user behavior regarding energy consumption. The future of the electric power industry and the growth of smart grid systems will have power quality devices based on data science calculations and transformations on such large datasets.

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